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A Two-Stage Hybrid Model by Using Artificial Neural Networks as Feature Construction Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

We propose a two-stage hybrid approach with neural networks as the new feature construction algorithms for bankcard response classifications. The hybrid model uses a very simple neural network structure as the new feature construction tool in the first stage, then the newly created features are used as the additional input variables in logistic regression in the second stage. The model is compared with the traditional one-stage model in credit customer response classification. It is observed that the proposed two-stage model outperforms the one-stage model in terms of accuracy, the area under ROC curve, and KS statistic. By creating new features with the neural network technique, the underlying nonlinear relationships between variables are identified. Furthermore, by using a very simple neural network structure, the model could overcome the drawbacks of neural networks in terms of its long training time, complex topology, and limited interpretability.

KEYWORDS

Hybrid Model, Neural Network, Feature Construction, Logistic Regression, Bankcard Response Model

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An Efficient Feature Selection Model for IGBO Text

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ABSTRACT

The development in Information Technology (IT) has encouraged the use of Igbo Language in text creation, online news reporting, online searching and articles publications. As the information stored in text format of this language is increasing, there is need for an intelligent text-based system for proper management of the data. The selection of optimal set of features for processing plays vital roles in text-based system. This paper analyzed the structure of Igbo text and designed an efficient feature selection model for an intelligent Igbo text-based system. It adopted Mean TF-IDF measure to select most relevant features on Igbo text documents represented with two word-based n-gram text representation (unigram and bigram) models. The model is designed with Object-Oriented Methodology and implemented with Python programming language with tools from Natural Language Toolkits (NLTK). The result shows that bigram represented text gives more relevant features based on the language semantics.

KEYWORDS

Feature Selection, Igbo Language, Igbo Text Pre-Processing, Text Representation

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